

بلوچستان میں شادی بیاہ کے موقع پر موسیقی، ونی اور سوار کی مروجہ رسوم و رواج
کا شریعت اسلامی کی روشنی میں تحقیقی و تنقیدی جائزہ

A research review in the light of Islam's Shari'a of Music and Sawar/Woni of Marriage in Balochistan

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Abstract

In summary, today in different areas of Balochistan, there are many customs related to marriage, among them, the first ritual is music in marriage. It is illegal from the point of view of Quran, Hadith, jurists, mystics, mystics and modern scholars, so it is necessary that the ritual of music and music on the occasion of marriage in Balochistan should be banned so that our marriage is not according to the ritual, but according to the Sunnah of the Prophet, which will make this marriage a happiness. Marriage in Balochistan is another ritual of "wini" and "sawar". It requires that when a man kills, three girls are given as brides in return for the blood of this one murder. Most of the girls are little girls. This work is done by the guardians and guardians of the girl. And when these girls get married and need to be married, the same attitude and behavior is done to the young girls which was done to the slaves in the past, this custom is popular among Pashtuns as well as Punjabis and Sindhis and it is called "Wini" and "Sawar" and this custom is very ugly and there are many prohibitions, so the Sharia has prohibited it. However, this ritual has been popular for hundreds of years and in the present era, efforts are being made by the government and the general reformers and intellectuals to end this ritual and a lot of efforts have been made for it, but the ritual has not ended yet, but the lack of it has been noticed.

Keywords: Marriage customs, Music prohibition, Wani/Sawar tradition, Child brides, Sharia restrictions

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